

Transport of ammonium across prokaryotic cell membranes

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ABSTRACT

Ammonium transport proteins are present in all domains of life. Recently, four ammonium transport protein (Amt) structures were resolved at high resolution: the AmtB from the eubacteria *E. coli*, the Amt-1 from the hyperthermophilic archaeon *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*, the Rh50 from *Nitrosomonas europaea* and the human Rhesus glycoprotein RhCG. All these proteins share a remarkable degree of structural homology, with 11 transmembrane helices per monomer. A narrow, non-continuous and hydrophobic pore, located at the center of each monomer of the trimeric Amt-1, is thought to be the substrate channel. At the extracellular channel cleft, ammonium selectivity and recruitment presumably occurs via a cation- π interaction with the side chain of W137 that are stabilized by hydrogen bonds to the side chain of S208. The side chains of F96 and F204 block the channel continuity. Next to them the side chains of two highly conserved histidine residues (H157 and H305) are bridged by an H-bond, with their edges pointing into the cavity. The role of these histidine residues is not clearly understood yet.

KEYWORDS: membrane proteins, ammonium transport proteins, protein crystallography, *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen is essential for many processes and is crucial for any life-form on Earth. It is a component in all amino acids, is incorporated in

proteins, and is present in the bases that make up nucleic acids. It resides in the chemical structure of almost all neurotransmitters and is a defining component of alkaloids, which are biological molecules produced by many organisms.

Diverse organisms are able to use many nitrogen sources, including ammonia, nitrate and dinitrogen, and a variety of amino acids and other nitrogenous organic compounds. Whereas animals only use nitrogen-containing amino acids as a nitrogen source, microorganisms and plants mostly depend on the uptake of ammonium. One exception is reductive dinitrogen fixation. This complex process is carried out by nitrogen-fixing bacteria present in the soil. These bacteria are able to reduce N_2 to NH_3 by using the nitrogenase complex system. This process requires the hydrolysis of 16 equivalents of ATP and is accompanied by the co-formation of one molecule of H_2 [1].

Ammonium can also be generated from molecular nitrogen by nitrogen-fixing bacteria in some plant cells, such as rhizobia in legume root nodule cells, and ammonium transporter proteins have been implicated in the transfer of ammonium from these bacteria to the plant cytoplasm [2].

The transport of ammonium across cell membranes is a process of fundamental importance in almost all living organisms. As the charged NH_4^+ and uncharged NH_3 molecules are in equilibrium, with a pKa of 9.25 in aqueous solutions, NH_4 is the predominant form (c.a. 99%) at a typical cytosolic pH. At high ammonium concentrations in the environment (for example, above 1 mM), passive membrane permeation of the uncharged species can be sufficient to promote cell growth in the

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cases of enteric bacteria and fungi. However, at lower concentrations, when diffusion becomes insufficient for sustaining cell growth, ammonium transport proteins (Amt) are needed [3].

Ammonium activity was first discovered in filamentous fungi [4]. Uptake activity was detected only under starvation conditions and was measured using the substrate analogue ^{14}C -methylammonium, which was shown to accumulate against its concentration gradient. In 1994, the first two amt (ammonium transporter) genes from *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were sequenced [5, 6, 7]. During 2002, Merrick and co-workers overexpressed and purified AmtB in large amounts by Ni^{2+} affinity chromatography from *E. coli* cells [8]. They showed that AmtB forms highly stable trimers in the membrane that remain preserved during the purification procedure. The crystal structure of AmtB was later solved by two independent groups [9, 10]. Currently, three other Amt structures are known at high resolution: the Amt-1 from the hyperthermophilic archaeon *Archaeoglobus fulgidus* [11], the Rh50 from *Nitrosomonas europaea* [12, 13] and the human Rhesus glycoprotein RhCG [14]. With increasing accumulation of knowledge on these proteins and with further genome sequences becoming available, we now know that Amt proteins are ubiquitous and form an independent family of membrane proteins. For example, a study based on sequence analysis has revealed that the human Rhesus (Rh) blood groups are related to the Amt proteins [15]. Functional complementation experiments performed later have demonstrated that human Rh proteins can indeed rescue the growth of a yeast mutant deficient in ammonium uptake [16] and thus function as Amt proteins. The Rh family [17] comprises the erythroid blood group antigens and non-erythroid homologues that are expressed in the kidney, liver, skin, ovary, testes and central nervous system [18, 19]. Although most evidences suggest that Rh proteins are part of the Amt/Mep/Rh family, they also have been proposed by some researchers to be gas channels for CO_2 [20, 21, 22, 23]. Supportive, but controversial, evidence for this is that at elevated CO_2 concentrations, the expression level of Rh1 in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* increases [24]. Since RhAG homologues are also found in slime moulds, sponges, nematodes

and fruit flies, these proteins were probably derived from Mep/Amt proteins and originated later in evolution from a RhAG-like ancestor [25, 26].

2. Ammonium transport proteins of *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*

Archaeoglobus fulgidus is an anaerobic marine hyperthermophilic archaeon. It was first isolated in 1987 from marine hydrothermal vents in Italy by Stetter *et al.* [27, 28]. Later, it was also found at 75 °C in the hot oil-field water of an oil production platform in the North Sea [29]. Analysis of the 16S and the 23S rRNA sequences showed a close relationship to the methanogenic Archaea [30]. Like other hyperthermophiles, *A. fulgidus* can survive in extreme environments. It grows between 60 °C and 95 °C, with a growth optimum at 83 °C and a minimum division time of 4 h. *A. fulgidus* is stable at pH values between 5.5 and 7.5 and is able to adapt its nutritional requirements to environmental changes. Electron micrographs have shown its cell morphology to be irregular coccoid to disk-shaped, with monopolar flagella and a glycoprotein envelope. However, it lacks an inelastic cell wall component. The diameter of each cell is 0.3-1.0 μm . Environmental stress, for e.g. high temperatures, extreme pH below 5 or high concentrations of toxic substances such as chromium (VI) and other toxic metals, antibiotics or oxygen, induces the creation of a biofilm [31]. This biofilm is a fibrous heterogeneous material with a morphologically variable structure consisting of protein, polysaccharides and various metals. Biofilms are considered to be the stress-response mechanism of archaea and are also found among other organisms such as *Archaeoglobus profundus*, *Methanococcus jannaschii* or *Methanobacterium thermoautotrophicum*. *Archaeoglobus* species contribute to deep subsurface oil-well “souring” by iron sulphide, which causes the corrosion of iron and steel in oil- and gas-processing systems.

In 1997, the whole genome of *A. fulgidus* was sequenced as the first genome of a sulphur-metabolizing organism [32]. *A. fulgidus* is categorized as a chemolithoautotroph organism. The *A. fulgidus* genome is a circular chromosome, roughly half the size of that of *E. coli*, with

2.18 million base pairs (bp) and containing approximately 2486 predicted genes. One observation concerning its genome analysis is the absence of several important eubacterial biochemical pathways such as glycolysis, the pentose phosphate pathway, the Entner-Doudoroff pathway and gluconeogenesis. Even the citric acid pathway is absent. *A. fulgidus* uses a C1 pathway to degrade acetyl-CoA. Furthermore, neither energy-conserving pathways of the nitrogen cycle nor a nitrogenase system have been found. In addition, three homologues of Amt proteins are present. The reasons for this amt gene multiplicity have not yet been demonstrated. Amt proteins are thought to differ in their affinity to their substrate, such that the cell is able to control the ammonium uptake into the cells, as a response to environmental changes [33].

In the genome of *A. fulgidus*, the three ammonium transporter genes are found in two separate loci (*amt-1*, *amt-2* and *amt-3*), each one followed by a gene that belongs to a PII family member (glnK). Among the three GlnK proteins from *A. fulgidus*, GlnK1 and GlnK3 share 98% amino acid sequence identity, whereas GlnK2 is the most distinct (60% identity with GlnK1 and 59% with GlnK3). The genomic location of GlnK2, in a gene cluster with the ammonium transporter Amt-2, a putative zinc hydrolase (AF1748) and the ammonium transporter Amt-3 followed by its corresponding GlnK-3 protein, suggests that GlnK and Amt proteins are specific interaction partners, as has been shown for the GlnK/AmtB pair [34].

The amino acid sequences of Amt-1 and Amt-3 show 64.2% sequence identity, with Amt-1 and Amt-2 having 39.7%, and Amt-2 and Amt-3 possessing 40.6%. Amt-1 and Amt-3 have 11 transmembrane helices without a leader peptide cleavage side. Amt-2 has a 19-amino-acid longer cytosolic C-terminus compared with Amt-1 and Amt-3. This region has been proposed to have regulatory functions [35]. Amt-2 has higher homologies (42.4%) to the *E. coli* Amt-B (than the two others), which also shows a longer C-terminal region.

3. Crystal structure of Amt-1 from *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*

The X-ray structure of Amt-1 from *A. fulgidus* was initially determined at 1.54 Å, and later

improved to 1.45 Å [36]. Crystal structures with and without ammonium or methylammonium were also determined by soaking the native protein crystals in solutions of ammonium or methylammonium [36].

The tertiary structure shows that the protein crosses the membrane with 11 helices and that it homotrimerizes in the quaternary structure. Each monomer incorporates a hydrophobic channel in between relatively polar cytoplasmic and periplasmic vestibules. Consistent with the “positive inside-out” rule for membrane proteins [37], the trimer of Amt-1 has a net negative charge on the periplasmic surface and a net positive charge on the cytoplasmic side. The residues from helices VI, VII, VIII and IX of one monomer interact with the helices I, II and III of neighbouring monomers, so that the protein homotrimerizes in a three-fold symmetric fashion. The structure has revealed its pseudo-two-fold symmetric organization within the monomer itself, in which membrane-spanning helices I-V are related to helices VI-X by a quasi-two-fold axis that lies in the mid-membrane plane. This pseudo-two-fold architecture is well known from other membrane proteins such as lactose permease [38] or the chloride channels [39] among many others.

Although no open channel crosses the protein, a closer inspection of the structure strongly indicates that substrate translocation occurs through a pore located at the centre of each monomer between the pseudosymmetry-related helical domains. The pore shows a vestibule on its extracellular and intracellular sides. The recruitment and selectivity site is presumably formed by the aromatic ring of W137 and S208. A cation π -interaction between W137 and NH_4^+ stabilized by a hydrogen bond to S208 might explain the high affinity to NH_4^+ and the exclusion of other monovalent cations, such as K^+ (no hydrogen-bonding interactions) and water (not a cation). Direct experimental evidence for this binding site has not yet been obtained and an assignment based on crystallographic data is impossible because water and ammonium have an identical number of electrons.

Further below, the transport pathway is blocked by the side chains of two conserved residues F96 and F204. F204 has an elevated B factor in

comparison with the surrounding amino acids, indicating an increased mobility of this residue in the structure. Based on this observation, some degree of conformational rearrangement is thought to occur, so that the substrate can pass this barrier and reach the cytoplasmic side. To test the hydrophobic nature of the pore, a hydrophobic gas, xenon, has been introduced into the crystals of Amt-1 under pressure. Two out of 15 xenon atoms per monomer have been found in the lumen of the pore, emphasizing the hydrophobicity of the substrate channel with the exception of two histidine residues. The side chains of these residues (H157 and H305), both highly conserved among the entire Amt family, lie adjacent, with their imidazole ring edges facing the cavity such that a hydrogen bond is formed between their δ nitrogens. Their high conservation and localization deep inside the hydrophobic pore have led to the proposal of a functional role for this pair in substrate deprotonation/reprotonation. This hypothesis, however, still lacks supporting experimental evidence.

4. CONCLUSION

Recent years have seen exciting developments towards our understanding of the function of Amt proteins. High-quality structural information has become available and functional data have been collected through a multitude of techniques. Nevertheless, the results are inconclusive with respect to some of the most fundamental questions concerning Amt transport. Based on the crystal structures of these proteins, theoretical calculations have been presented, but all follow the pre-assumption of passive transport. Ammonium has been predicted to enter the protein in its charged form and to become deprotonated upon reaching the histidine pair deep inside the membrane; however, further fate of the lone proton has not yet been investigated. Further experiments will be required to examine closely the functionality of Amt proteins *in vivo* and *in vitro*.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

This paper does not have any conflict of interest.

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